

Oncogene targeted next-generation-sequencing in extracranial arteriovenous malformations

Key words: arteriovenous malformation, NGS, somatic mutation, phenotype, genotype, angioarchitecture, Schobinger, ISSVA classification

SM Bernhard^{*1,2,3}, A Tuleja^{*1,2}, Y Doering^{1,2,4,5}, E Vassella⁶, U Amstutz⁷, C Zweier⁸, J Roessler^{9,10,11}, L M Boon^{12,13}, M Vikkula^{12,13}, F Haupt¹⁴, G Hamvas^{1,2}, M Schindewolf^{1,2}, R Kammer^{1,2}, I Baumgartner¹⁵

- ¹⁾ Division of Angiology, Swiss Cardiovascular Center, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, Bern, Switzerland
- ²⁾ Department for BioMedical Research (DBMR), University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
- ³⁾ Vascular Center, Bienna Hospital Center, Bienna, Switzerland
- ⁴⁾ Institute for Cardiovascular Prevention (IPEK), Ludwig-Maximilians-University Munich (LMU), 80336 Munich, Germany
- ⁵⁾ DZHK (German Centre for Cardiovascular Research), Partner Site Munich Heart Alliance, 80336 Munich, Germany
- ⁶⁾ Institute of Tissue Medicine and Pathology, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
- ⁷⁾ Department of Clinical Chemistry, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, University of Bern, Switzerland
- ⁸⁾ Department of Human Genetics, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
- ⁹⁾ Division of Paediatric Hematology and Oncology, Department of Paediatrics, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
- ¹⁰⁾ Division of Pediatric Hematology and Oncology, Department of Pediatrics and Adolescent Medicine, Medical Center-University of Freiburg, Faculty of Medicine, University of Freiburg, Freiburg, Germany.
- ¹¹⁾ Department of Vascular Medicine, National Reference Center of Rare Lymphatic and Vascular Diseases, UA11 INSERM - UM IDESP, Campus Santé, Montpellier Cedex 5, France.
- ¹²⁾ Center for Vascular Anomalies, Division of Plastic Surgery, VASCERN VASCA European Reference Centre, Saint Luc University Hospital, Brussels, Belgium
- ¹³⁾ Human Molecular Genetics, de Duve Institute, University of Louvain, Brussels, Belgium
- ¹⁴⁾ Department of Diagnostic, Interventional and Pediatric Radiology, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland
- ¹⁵⁾ Vasc Alliance AG; Bern Center for Vascular Medicine and Interventions, Schaanzlihalde 1, Bern, Switzerland

Corresponding author:

Sarah M Bernhard, MD

Division for Angiology, Swiss Cardiovascular Centre, University Hospital Bern

3010 Bern, Switzerland

Phone: +41 31 632 50 00

Email: sarah.bernhard@insel.ch

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Abstract

Background

Most isolated congenital vascular malformations are genetically characterized by somatic variants in various genes. However, large clinical variability challenges the analysis of correlations between genotype and phenotype.

Objectives

In sporadic extracranial arteriovenous malformation (AVM), mosaic-activating variants in the RAS/MAPK and PTEN signaling pathways have been described. Our aim was to distinguish AVM phenotypes based on clinical and angiographic findings in relation to corresponding pathogenic variants.

Methods

We reviewed patients with angiographically verified AVM in our prospective Bernese VAScular COngenital Malformation (VASCOM) cohort, in whom a genetic study of the affected tissue using high-throughput sequencing by the TruSight Oncology 500 panel (TSO500) had been performed. Each patient's initial clinical evaluation, imaging and histopathologic studies were assessed concerning patient and family history, symptoms, longitudinal overgrowth, soft tissue hypertrophy, angiographic classification and histologic confirmation of AVM.

Results

Overall, 35 patients (16 males and 19 females) between 8 to 59 years were included for analysis. Most of the AVMs (77%) were located in the extremities. In 49% of cases, more than one tissue compartment was involved. We detected known variants in *MAP2K1* (n=9), *KRAS* (n=7), *RASA1* (n=1), but also variants in other genes of the RAS pathway (*RIT1*, *PTPN11*). We also identified alterations in the PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling pathway with a *PIK3CA* variant (n=2), not yet associated with extra-cranial AVM. AVM with *KRAS* variants were more diffuse, involving whole extremities and were frequently associated with ulcerations (71% vs 11%) and longitudinal overgrowth (86% vs 22%), while AVM with *MAP2K1* variants were located mainly in hands and feet, and less frequently presented with overgrowth and ulcerations.

Conclusions

Though a larger number of cases would be required to draw definite conclusions, our study contributes to characterizing the molecular landscape of extracranial AVMs and points to a genotype-phenotype correlation regarding variants in *MAP2K1* and *KRAS*.

Introduction

Congenital vascular malformations are rare structural anomalies of blood and lymphatic vessels that can occur in any part of the body and with variable clinical consequences, ranging from harmless asymptomatic birthmarks to deadly congestive heart failure (1, 2). The current classification by the International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies (ISSVA) is based on the synopsis of various sources of information including clinical, imaging, and genetic assessments (3). However, attempts at systematic comparisons of genotypes and phenotypes indicate that additional careful analyses of clinical details are necessary to interpret associations more precisely. This will be necessary to address the disease more specifically by means of molecularly targeted treatment (4).

Normal cells can become abnormal via (a succession of) genetic alterations. Application of next generation sequencing (NGS) to decode defined sets of individual genes to detect genetic variants offers new insights into pathophysiological mechanisms underlying a variety of diseases. Disease-targeted (DT) genetic panel testing has become a promising approach in oncology and for individualized molecularly targeted cancer therapy (5). Recent research also identified genetic alterations, which occur during embryogenesis and result in somatic mosaic pathogenic mutations as underlying causes for most congenital vascular malformations (6, 7). In arteriovenous malformations (AVM) various mosaic-activating mutations have been described (8, 9). However, while the knowledge about the pathophysiological and genetic background in intracranial AVMs and AVMs associated with hereditary hemorrhagic teleangiectasia or capillary malformation – arteriovenous malformation is considerable (10, 11), there are much less documented insights regarding extracranial AVMs. Extracranial AVMs are often grouped as a seemingly unified overall group, although clinical presentation and genetic background may well differ.

Extracranial AVMs can occur as 1) sporadic isolated forms, 2) combined with additional dysplasia of the capillary, venous or lymphatic system, 3) as complex syndromic forms with other anomalies or 4) they may also run in families (12-14). Though familial clustering has been described in some cases, the vast majority of AVMs are sporadic and related to somatic mutations (7, 15). In the context of extracranial AVMs, there are

5 patient series published using high-throughput next generation sequencing (NGS). One study identified a KRAS variants in 2 out of 49 patients with AVM affecting a finger and a leg using the smMIP panel (21 genes) (16). Another study found either *KRAS* or *MAP2K1* variants in 9 out of 25 patients with extracranial AVM (17). An additional study identified a variant in the RAS/MAPK-pathway in 18 out of 23 patients using a customized gene panel of 106 genes (18). Another study identified pathogenic and/or likely pathogenic variants in 37 out of 54 patients with AVMs using a customized gene panel of 37 genes (19). A more recent multicentric retrospective study reviewed the results of the genetic analysis of core needle biopsy obtained by Sanger sequencing for *KRAS*, *HRAS*, *NRAS*, *BRAF* and *MAP2K1* and identified 29 patients of which 24 presented an AVM (20). However, the association of the detected genotypes to specific phenotypes remains unclear, and the increasing number of identified, potentially causal genetic variants indicates that additional analyses of clinical details are mandatory to be able to better interpret and draw conclusions for future diagnostic and therapeutic approaches.

The aim of this study is to analyze the angioarchitecture and clinically distinguishing features of patients with extracranial AVMs in correlation with their genetic variants identified by ultradeep sequencing allowing identification of variants at an allele frequency down to 1%.

Materials and Methods

Patient cohort and data management

The University Hospital of Bern is a referral center for the treatment of congenital vascular malformation in Switzerland. A clinic-based registry of patients with peripheral congenital vascular malformations was initiated in 2008 to collect information on demographics and phenotype of the patients and has been converted into a prospective monitored cohort since 2018. Detailed data on demographic baseline and clinical characteristics, familial disease burden, hereditary diseases, treatment, follow-up, laboratory data and results of diagnostic imaging are registered in an HRA-conform (Human Research Act) electronic database. All patients sign a general informed consent for coded data analysis. The prospective Bernese VAScular COngenital Malformation (VASCOM) cohort at the University Hospital of Bern, comprises 80 angiographically verified patients with AVM (21).

Baseline demographic data, including gender and age, were collected at first diagnosis. The attending physician systematically filled in a standardized electronic worksheet including patient's history (pain, recurrent bleeding, recurrent infection, reduced exercise capacity), objective findings from imaging and laboratory evaluation as well as clinical examination (limb overgrowth, swelling, localized increase in skin temperature).

Pain was recorded semi quantitatively using a numeric rating score (NRS) between 1 and 10, with 1 defined as no pain and 10 as the worst pain the patient could imagine (22). Limb overgrowth was objectively assessed by either measurement of the distance between the anterior-superior-iliac spine to the lateral malleolus while standing, long-leg radiography or bone length measurement in MRI. A history of epiphysiodesis of the affected limb for limb length correction was equally recorded as longitudinal overgrowth. Soft tissue hypertrophy was qualitatively assessed by visual estimation on MRI and photo documentation. Soft tissue hypertrophy was assessed on MRI to differentiate blood filled vessel volume and edema from soft tissue hypertrophy, except for one patient in whom no MRI had been performed, but who had clinically evident longitudinal and circumferential overgrowth of one leg.

Patients were classified according to the Schobinger classification, a staging system to define hyper-dynamic circulatory signs and symptoms of vascular malformations. Stage I was defined as quiescent disease, stage II as local expansion, stage III as destruction (ulceration or gangrene) of surrounding tissue due to ischemic steal and stage IV as decompensation with cardiac failure and symptomatic local steal syndrome, respectively (23). On first presentation, the anatomical location and hemodynamic characterization of the lesion was recorded by duplex ultrasound, digital subtraction angiography (DSA) and in all but one case by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

We further applied the angiographic classification according to Wayne Yakes for describing the type of nidus of the AVM (24) with the addition of the capillary-venule type (CV) as a postcapillary variant of microfistular AVM (CV-AVM) (25, 26). Two independent readers analyzed the angiograms in a random order to classify the type of AVM and angioarchitecture of the AVM nidus. In case of disagreement, an agreement was reached by consent between the two readers.

Tissue sample collection

The clinical VASCOM database process was expanded by the implementation of standardized congenital vascular malformation tissue harvesting. In this context, in all patients undergoing invasive treatments, a punch biopsy is performed. Tissue samples are directly processed for subsequent DNA preparation (snap frozen). A standardized tissue harvesting box is prepared for every patient with a biopsy scheduled. Pre-labeled color-coded tubes are filled with tissue fragments and stored in the holder to be snap frozen with isopentane and transported on dry ice to the pathology laboratory. Remaining tissue is stored in the Tissue Biobank Bern (TBB).

Next generation sequencing (NGS)

TSO 500 panel enables comprehensive genomic profiling of tissue samples. Originally designed to identify gene variants implicated in various solid tumor types, it also comprises all important somatic mutations described for congenital vascular malformations (7).

Moreover, the assay targets all exonic regions of 523 genes for assessment of all DNA variant types based on Illumina SBS sequencing technology.

DNA extraction from frozen tissue was performed using a Qiagen® tissue Microkit. Between 35 and 80 ng of DNA were sheared on a Covaris E220 ultrasonicator following the manufacturer's instruction. DNA fragments were end repaired and adapters containing unique molecular identifiers (UMIs) were ligated to each fragment end following the manufacturer's protocol. Fragments enriched by capture hybridization were analyzed by high-throughput sequencing on a NovaSeq 6000 instrument (Illumina) applying the TruSight Oncology 500 (TSO 500) panel. TSO500 alignment and variant calling was performed using the TSO500 bioinformatics pipeline 2.1.0. UMI-filtered total read counts were 117 mio ±31 mio, median exon coverage was 1086 ±375, median DNA insert size 142 ±17, and % aligned reads ~97.5 ±2.5 allowing for the identification of variants at an allele frequency down to 1%.

Sources of broad population frequencies, that were used for auto-classification of benign variations, include dbSNP (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/projects/SNP>), the NHLBI Exome Sequencing Project (evs.gs.washington.edu/EVS), and the 1000 Genomes Project (<http://www.1000genomes.org>). Annotations of oncogenic effects of identified variants was retrieved from the OncoKB precision oncology knowledge base developed at Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center (27).

Statistical analysis

In view of the small sample size, the statistical analysis was limited to descriptive statistics. Categorical data is presented as number and percentage, continuous data as mean with standard deviation.

Results

Phenotypic characteristics

General characteristics concerning localization, affected tissue compartments, Schobinger stage, and signs and symptoms of the 35 patients are displayed in **Table I**.

Mean age of the patients was 35 years (ranging from 8 to 59 years). There were 19 (54%) females and 16 (46%) males. Most AVMs (26 of 35, 74%) were located in the extremities. The other localizations comprised one isolated pulmonary AVM, two AVMs of the thoracic wall, two AVMs of the nose, one AVM of the left external ear, one AVM of the upper and lower lip and two AVMs of the neck. Hand or foot, as distal parts of the extremities, were involved in 15 of 26 (58%) cases. There was a wide range of tissue compartments affected (skin, n=6; subcutis, n=22; interstitial space n=3; muscle, n=20; lung tissue, n=1; bone, n=3). More than one tissue compartment was involved in 17 (49%) cases.

The majority of AVMs were sporadic AVMs according to the ISSVA classification (unifocal n=33; multifocal n=2). Additional soft tissue hypertrophy was present in 19 (54%), and longitudinal overgrowth of the affected extremity in 11 (31%) cases, respectively.

There were three patients with Parkes Weber syndrome (CM, AVM, overgrowth; PKWS), and one patient with PTEN-Hamartoma-Tumor-Syndrome (PHTS) and multifocal AVMs of the extremities.

The comparison of individual angiographic AVM types (angioarchitecture according to the Wayne Yakes angiographic classification) versus detected genetic variants is shown in **Table II**.

Genotypic characteristics

We detected variants described to be related to extracranial AVMs in 18 of 35 patients. Among these patients there was one with PTEN-Hamartoma Tumor syndrome and a confirmed heterozygous *PTEN* germline mutation.

As shown in Table II, already previously described variants were found in AVM tissues with low (<15%) VAF in *MAP2K1* (n=9), *KRAS* (n=7) and *RASA1* (n=1). We found a *RIT1* variant in a patient with an isolated intramuscular AVM of the neck, which we recently confirmed in a zebra fish model (28). There were three additional variants with VAF <15% not yet described in extracranial fast-flow malformations (AVM, AVF), but related to oncogene pathways implicated in vascular malformations, thus pointing to a pathogenic relevance (7). These included a *PIK3CA* variant in a patient with capillary malformation, left leg circumferential and longitudinal overgrowth and microfistular CV-AVM and a *PIK3CA* variant in a patient with an isolated intramuscular AVM of the left thigh, and a *PTPN11* variant in a patient with atypical varicose veins in the context of a microfistular CV-AVM of both legs. Clinical images and corresponding angiographies are displayed in **Figure 1**. An other patient harbored both a somatic *PTEN* variant and a somatic *MAP2K1* variant (**Figure 2**).

We detected additional somatic variants of unknown significance (VUS) in all but two of the 35 patients. In 14 patients, the VAF were <15%. For the remaining patients the VUS had a VAF of > 40%, being compatible with a possible germline variants. In 6 patients (17%), we detected only VUS with VAF < 15%, and in 7 patients (20%) only VUSs with VAF around 50%. The additional VUS are displayed in supplemental **Table S I**.

Phenotype-genotype correlations

We could not identify any genetic clusters in reference to the location of the AVM or differences concerning infiltration of different tissues, and we observed no particular genotype related to any of the specific angiographic phenotypes. For example, CV-AVM, a form of post-capillary microfistular AVM we described recently (26), revealed variants in *PTPN11*, *KRAS*, *RASA1* and *PIK3CA*. We neither identified a correlation between micro-fistular AVM (i.e. types IV and CV-AVM) nor macro-fistular AVM (types II and III) and genotype. **Figure 2** shows the example of three patients with isolated AVM type IIIb, harboring variants either in *PTEN*, or VUS in *ZBTB7A* or *MAP3K13* with VAF ~50%, hinting to a probable germline context of the detected variants.

Three patients who responded with an unusually strong progression of an AVM type IV and postinterventional localized tissue hypertrophy after ethanol embolosclectherapy had variants in *MAP2K1*, *KRAS* and *RIT1*, respectively.

Variants in *MAP2K1* were associated with an interstitial type IV AVM component in 66% of the patients (n=6/9), while variants in *KRAS* were associated with an interstitial type IV AVM in 43% (n=3/7) and CV-AVM in 29% (n=2/7) of the patients, respectively (**Figure 3**). Concerning the Schobinger classification, there were more patients with stage III (n=5/7) and IV (n=1/7) in the *KRAS* variant group, compared to stage II (n=8/9) and III (n=1/9) in the *MAP2K1* variant group. In four of the nine patients with *MAP2K1* variants, the AVM was localized on the hands, whereas in five of the seven patients with *KRAS* variants the AVM was located in the lower extremities. Longitudinal overgrowth was present in 6/7 patients (86%) with *KRAS* variants and only in 2/9 patients (22%) with *MAP2K1* variants.

Discussion

In this study, we present the targeted NGS results on tissue biopsies of 35 patients with extra-cranial AVMs. This is the largest series of tissue NGS in extracranial AVM, not located only in head and neck (74% extremities, 17% head/neck). A likely pathogenic variant was identified in 22 AVM patients.

Most of the variants were in *MAP2K1* and *KRAS* in the RAS-MAPK-ERK-pathway. However, a variant in the *RASA1* gene was also detected. *RASA1* mutations have been detected in CM-AVM patients (8, 29). Additionally, we detected likely pathogenic somatic variants in genes, which have not yet been described in extracranial AVMs, but are also related to the RAS-MAPK-ERK-pathway, such as *PTPN11* and the recently described *RIT1* variant (28), as well as *PTEN* and *PIK3CA* variants related to the *mTOR* pathway. *RIT1* as well as *PTPN11* variants have been described in the context of RASopathies such as Noonan- and LEOPARD syndrome, but also in various cancers such as neuroblastoma, melanoma and acute myeloid leukemia (30). *RIT1* is a RAS-related small GTPase (31-33) and *PTPN11*, a member of the protein tyrosine phosphatase (PTP) family, activating RAS-signaling (33-35). *PIK3CA* mutations, in contrast, have been described in slow-flow vascular malformations and in the syndromic context of *PIK3CA*-Related Overgrowth Spectrum (PROS) (36-38). Recently the general role of *PIK3CA* mutations in angiogenesis has been described,

which might explain why this variant in a high-flow context might also be involved in extracranial AVM (39). We detected *PIK3CA* variants in a patient with microfistular AVFs, an extensive capillary malformation of the affected extremity and associated leg overgrowth (40), as well as an isolated intramuscular AVM of the thigh. *PIK3CA* mutations have not been described in extracranial AVM yet, but an insertion-deletion (indel) variant in PI3K (E109_I112delinsD) is presumably activating (41). *PTEN* mutations are known to cause AVM in the context of PHTS but have not been described as somatic variants in sporadic extracranial AVM (42).

The role of the additionally detected VUS and potential germline variants with VAF >20% remains unclear.

Exact phenotyping is crucial for being able to interpret potential genotype-phenotype associations. As the clinical presentation and the tendency for ulceration, defined as a more severe Schobinger classification, depend largely on the exact location of the AVM, this classification probably cannot be used to compare AVMs in different body regions (14). In this context, the interpretation of the more severe Schobinger stages in patients with *KRAS* variants, which were located at the lower extremities in 6/7 patients, compared to patients with *MAP2K1* variants, which were located at the hands or upper extremities in 5/9 patients, is difficult. AVM associated phleb- and/or lymphedema is more likely to occur at the lower extremities and can worsen the skin condition. Skin under tension over cartilage is more fragile per se, which puts nose and ears at risk for ulcerations.

In order to find reliable and objective phenotypic characteristics, we opted to assess soft tissue hypertrophy and longitudinal overgrowth. In this context it is important to separate swelling (i.e. edema or blood filled vessels) from tissue hypertrophy (**Figure 4**). Presence or absence of hypertrophy seems especially important, as soft tissue hypertrophy and overgrowth might indicate the involvement of other cell types than only endothelial cells. When comparing the two main groups of *MAP2K1* and *KRAS* variants, there was only one patient with longitudinal overgrowth in the *MAP2K1* group, but 6/7 patients of the *KRAS* group, probably reflecting more diffusely affected tissues. However, this was not reflected in the variant allele frequency which was similar in both groups.

A second phenotypic characteristic, we used was the angiographic phenotype according to the Yakes classification with the addition of the microfistular variant of capillary-venule AVM (CV-AVM). As described above, the main difference between *MAP2K1* and *KRAS*-AVMs was the predominance of the interstitial type IV in all AVMs with *MAP2K1* variants. However, this series is too small to draw definite conclusions.

Previous treatments and possible reactions to treatment are an additional source for variability in clinical phenotype and angioarchitecture. Many of the patients have had previous surgical or interventional treatments in other centers. Incomplete AVM occlusion or excision is known to be able to trigger progression (12, 43-45), which could alter the angiographic phenotype. As detailed in the comments of Table 1, we observed a marked interstitial progression of type IV AVM after treatment in three cases with completely different genotypes (*MAP2K1*, *KRAS*, *RIT1*).

Main limitations in this study are the small number of patients and the exclusion of AV-fistulas (Yakes Type I), as they mainly occur in patients with hereditary hemorrhagic telangiectasia and in a visceral context, where biopsies would be risky. This is also why we do not have tissue from visceral AVMs, except one of the lungs, where a non-anatomical partial lung resection had been performed. In addition, one must take into account that we used an oncogene targeted panel, not dedicated for vascular malformations, but which permitted to reveal potentially pathogenic variants in this context which have not yet been described. Further studies using broader approaches such as whole exome sequencing are needed to confirm and broaden these findings. Another important issue is the potential selection bias concerning the location of the malformations, as our consultation is attached to the department for vascular medicine, probably leading to the more frequent detection of AVMs of the extremities. On the other hand, many of the existing publications are led by neurosurgeons, possibly leading to an overrepresentation of AVMs of the head and neck.

Conclusions

In accordance with El Sissy et al. (18), as well as Hernandez et al. (19) and Schmidt et al. (20) we see phenotypic differences between *MAP2K1*-AVMs compared to *KRAS*-AVMs. However, there is no definite assignment of higher aggressiveness to one or

the other variant. In our series, KRAS-AVMs were more diffuse, involving whole extremities (71%) and were associated with longitudinal overgrowth (86%) and tissue ulceration (71%), while MAP2K1-AVMs were found more in the periphery of an extremity (hands and feet), and displayed longitudinal overgrowth (22%) and ulcerations (11%) to a much lesser extent. To draw definite conclusions on genotype related phenotypes, the number of patients analyzed remains too small.

Larger series of patients need to be analyzed, ideally by whole exome sequencing in AVM tissue and corresponding blood samples with the aim to identify further mutations, which might act synergistically and could serve as new therapeutic targets for molecularly targeted therapies (16, 17, 46) . Further investigations can lead not only to the identification of new therapeutic options for patients with this rare but serious disease, but also to the identification of predictive markers for the progression, severity and phenotype of AVMs.

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Tables and figures

Table I: Overview of signs and symptoms related to the AVM

Patient number	Age at 1 st consultation	Sex	Location (compartment)	Schobinger stage	Symptoms	Soft tissue hypertrophy	Longitudinal overgrowth	Comments
1	44	F	right hand (sc, m)	II	pain, swelling	yes	no	interstitial progression + hypertrophy after treatment
2	59	F	right hand (sc, m)	II	pain, bleeding (sealed rupture of feeder aneurysm)	yes	no	aneurysms of feeder arteries
3	54	F	right hand (sc, m)	III	pain, recurrent ulcerations	no	no	elongated feeder arteries
4	19	F	Left foot (m)	II	pain	yes	no	
5	36	F	right hand (sc, m)	II	swelling, pain	no	no	elongated feeder arteries
6	29	M	Left leg (sc, m)	II	pain	yes	yes	elongated feeder arteries
7	18	M	Left elbow (m)	II	Pain, swelling	yes	no	
8	16	M	Left thoracic wall (m)	II	swelling	no	no	
9	23	M	Left leg (sk, sc)	II	Pain, swelling	yes	yes	
10	38	M	right neck (m)	II	pain, swelling	no	no	interstitial progression + hypertrophy after treatment
11	34	M	both legs (sc, b)	III	pain, atypical varicosis	no	no	bilateral involvement
12	51	M	Right leg and foot (sc)	III	pain, swelling, ulceration, recurrent infections	yes	yes	elongated feeder arteries
13	29	F	right leg (sk, sc, m)	IV	pain, recurrent ulceration, recurrent infection	yes	yes	Marfan syndrome; aneurysms of feeder arteries; interstitial progression after treatment
14	58	F	right leg and foot (sc)	III	recurrent ulceration, atypical varicosis	yes	yes	
15	50	M	right hand (sc, m)	III	pain	yes	yes	aneurysms of feeder arteries;
16	46	F	nose (sk, sc)	III	pain, ulceration	no	no	
17	39	F	right leg (m, sc)	II	pain	yes	yes	additional spinal AVM
18	18	M	Left leg (sc, m)	III	pain, ulceration, infection, atypical varicosis	yes	yes	
19	41	F	right leg (sk, sc, m)	II	pain, overgrowth	yes	yes	PKWS: CM, AVM, overgrowth
20	22	F	left leg right foot right arm (sc)	II	pain, swelling	no	no	PTEN-Hamartoma-Tumor-Syndrom (PHTS)
21	39	F	left leg and foot (sk, sc, m)	III	pain, recurrent ulcerations	yes	yes	PKWS: CM, AVM, overgrowth
22	33	F	Right leg (m)	I	pain	no	no	
23	57	F	left hand (sc)	I	pain	no	no	
24	58	M	right foot (it, b, sc)	III	ischemic bone erosion	yes	no	elongated feeder arteries
25	49	F	upper and lower lip (m)	II	bleeding	no	no	
26	30	M	left leg (sk, sc, m)	III	pain, swelling, recurrent ulcerations	yes	yes	PKWS: CM, AVM, overgrowth
27	34	F	left thoracic wall (m)	II	pain, swelling	yes	no	

28	44	M	Neck (it)	II	pain	yes	no	
29	29	F	lung (vo)	I	asymptomatic	no	no	
30	42	M	right foot (sc)	II	pain	no	no	elongated feeder arteries
31	24	M	left arm (it,b)	II	pain	yes	no	
32	8	F	right Hand (sc)	II	pain, swelling	no	no	
33	19	M	left ear (sc)	III	pain, swelling, papillomatous skin changes	no	no	
34	21	F	left foot (m)	II	pain	no	no	
35	56	M	nose (sc)	III	bleeding	no	no	

Affected tissue compartments are abbreviated as follows (sk = skin, sc = subcutaneous tissue, it = interstitial space, m = muscle, vo = visceral organs, b = bone).

Table II: Overview of phenotypic characteristics and detected variants in AVM tissue

Patient number	Age at 1 st consultation	Sex	Location (compartment)	Angiographic classification	Soft tissue hypertrophy	Longitudinal overgrowth	Variants	% VAF
1	44	F	right hand (sc, m)	IIIb, IV	yes	no	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>T)	<u>5.2</u>
2	59	F	right hand (sc, m)	IIIb, IV	yes	no	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>C)	<u>1.4</u>
3	54	F	right hand (sc, m)	II, IV	no	no	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>T)	<u>6.1</u>
4	19	F	Left foot (m)	IIIb, IV	yes	no	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.Gln56Pro (c.167A>C)	<u>12.7</u>
5	36	F	right hand (sc, m)	IV (II)	no	no	<u>PTEN</u> <u>MAP2K1</u> p.Cys124Tyr (c.371G>A) p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>T)	<u>1.7</u> <u>4.6</u>
6	29	M	Left leg (sc, m)	IIIb, II	yes	yes	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.Q58 E62del (c.173 187del)	<u>8.7</u>
7	18	M	Left elbow (m)	IIIb, IV	yes	no	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.K57N (c.171G>T)	11.5
8	16	M	Left thoracic wall (m)	IIIb, II	no	no	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.Q56P (c.167 168delinsCC)	10.3
9	23	M	Left leg (sk, sc)	IIIb, II	yes	yes	<u>MAP2K1</u> p.K57N (c.171G>T)	6.4
10	38	M	right neck (m)	II, IV	no	no	<u>RIT1</u> p.E98 T100delinsVPL (c.293 299delinsAGTTTAC)	6.0
11	34	M	both legs (sc, b)	CV	no	no	<u>PTPN11</u> p.Ser502Pro (c.1504T>C)	<u>5.1</u>
12	51	M	Right leg and foot (sc)	II (IV)	yes	yes	<u>KRAS</u> p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A)	<u>1.8</u>
13	29	F	right leg (sk, sc, m)	IIIb, II, IV	yes	yes	<u>KRAS</u> <u>FBN1 (germline)</u> p.Cys887Tyr (c.2660G>A)	<u>12.4</u> 50.7
14	58	F	right leg and foot (sc)	CV	yes	yes	<u>KRAS</u> p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A)	<u>3.2</u>
15	50	M	right hand (sc, m)	IIIb, II, IV	yes	yes	<u>KRAS</u> p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A)	<u>8.8</u>
16	46	F	nose (sk, sc)	II	no	no	<u>KRAS</u> p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A)	<u>11.5</u>
17	39	F	right leg (m, sc)	II (CV)	yes	yes	<u>KRAS</u> p.Gly12Val (c.35G>T)	<u>4.7</u>
18	18	M	Left leg (sc, m)	IIIb, II	yes	yes	<u>KRAS</u> p.G12D (c.35G>A)	<u>9.0</u>

19	41	F	right leg (sk, sc, m)	CV	yes	yes	<u>RASA1</u>	<u>p.P886Afs*12 (c.2654dupG)</u>	<u>6.2</u>
20	22	F	left leg right foot right arm (sc)	IIIb	no	no	<u>PTEN (germline)</u>	<u>c.635-2A>C</u>	<u>50.4</u>
21	39	F	left leg and foot (sk, sc, m)	CV	yes	yes	<u>PIK3CA</u>	<u>p.Arg108 Ile112del (c.323_337del)</u>	<u>10.5</u>
22	33	F	Right leg (m)	CV	no	no	<u>PIK3CA</u>	<u>p.E545K (c.1633G>A)</u>	<u>1.3</u>
23	57	F	left hand (sc)	CV	no	no	7 VUS		<5.0
24	58	M	right foot (it, b, sc)	II	yes	no	1 VUS		<5.0
25	49	F	upper and lower lip (m)	II	no	no	2 VUS		<5.0
26	30	M	left leg (sk, sc, m)	IIIb, II, IV	yes	yes	1 VUS		<5.0
27	34	F	left thoracic wall (m)	IIIb, II	yes	no	2 VUS		<5.0
28	44	M	Neck (it)	II	yes	no	1 VUS		<5.0
29	29	F	lung (vo)	II	no	no	VUS		~50.0
30	42	M	right foot (sc)	IIIb	no	no	VUS		~50.0
31	24	M	left arm (it,b)	II, IIIb	yes	no	VUS		~50.0
32	8	F	right Hand (sc)	CV	no	no	VUS		~50.0
33	19	M	left ear (sc)	II	no	no	VUS		~50.0
34	21	F	left foot (m)	IIIb	no	no	VUS		~50.0
35	56	M	nose (sc)	II, IV	no	no	VUS		~50.0

Angiographic classification is displayed according to Yakes types I to IV with the addition of CV (capillary-venule) AVM; VAF (variant allele frequency); mutations, previously reported for AVMs, are in **bold and underlined**; potentially significant new variants are underlined; additional VUS (variants of unknown significance) are displayed in normal writing.

Supplemental Table:

Patient number	Age at 1 st consultation	Sex	Location (compartment)	Angiographic classification	Schobinger	Symptoms	Soft tissue hypertrophy	Longitudinal overgrowth	MAP2K1	PREX2	SMARCA4	Other Variants	% VAF	Comments
1	44	F	right hand (sc, m)	IIIb, IV	II	pain, swelling	yes	no	<u>MAP2K1</u>			<u>p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>T)</u> p.Lys1171Arg (c.3512A>G)	<u>5.2</u> 50.9	interstitial progression + hypertrophy after treatment
2	59	F	right hand (sc, m)	IIIb, IV	II	pain, bleeding (sealed rupture of feeder aneurysm)	yes	no	<u>MAP2K1</u>	<u>SPTA1</u>	<u>MEF2B</u>	<u>p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>C)</u> p.Phe1085Val (c.3253T>G) p.Pro252Leu (c.755C>T)	<u>1.4</u> 50.8 48.0	aneurysms of feeder arteries
3	54	F	right hand (sc, m)	II, IV	III	pain, recurrent ulcerations	no	no	<u>MAP2K1</u>	<u>PREX2</u>	<u>SMARCA4</u>	<u>p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>T)</u> p.Val821AlafsTer19 (c.2462del) p.Pro1616Leu (c.4847C>T)	<u>6.1</u> 49.2 47.3	elongated feeder arteries

4	19	F	Left foot (m)	IIIb, IV	II	pain	yes	no	MAP2K1 BRCA2 BLM RAD51C EP300 PRKCI	p.Gln56Pro (c.167A>C) p.Asp191Val (c.572A>T) p.Val1244Ile (c.3730G>A) p.Arg292Ser (c.876A>C) p.Pro2031Ala (c.6091C>G) p.His319Tyr (c.955C>T)	12.7 49.1 53.7 45.2 45.3 46.0	
5	36	F	right hand (sc, m)	IV (II)	II	swelling, pain	no	no	PTEN MAP2K1 FGFR2 MSH2 ARID1B	p.Cys124Tyr (c.371G>A) p.Lys57Asn (c.171G>T) p.Tyr616Cys (c.1847A>G) p.Ala649Val (c.1946C>T) p.Pro1576Ser (c.4726C>T)	1.7 4.6 48.2 47.8 47.7	elongated feeder arteries
6	29	M	Left leg (sc, m)	IIIb, II	II	pain	yes	yes	MAP2K1 EML4	p.Q58 E62del (c.173 187del) p.D335G (c.1004A>G)	8.7 48.0	elongated feeder arteries
7	18	M	Left elbow (m)	IIIb, IV	II	Pain, swelling	yes	no	MAP2K1 ASXL2 IRS1 FGFR1 CDH1 ERBB4	p.K57N (c.171G>T) p.V243I (c.727G>A) p.E1102K (c.3304G>A) p.D351N (c.1051G>A) p.V454I (c.1360G>A) p.M1016T (c.3047T>C)	11.5 7.5 9.7 7.8 56.7 47.3	
8	16	M	Left thoracic wall (m)	IIIb, II	II	swelling	no	no	MAP2K1 SDHC TSHR NOTCH3 KEL	p.Q56P (c.167 168delinsCC) p.Y99N (c.295T>A) p.W520S (c.1559G>C) p.P115R (c.344C>G) p.A160V (c.479C>T)	10.3 0.9 48.0 50.4 47.7	
9	23	M	Left leg (sk, sc)	IIIb, II	II	Pain, swelling	yes	yes	MAP2K1 FLT4 LZTR0 TMEM127 LRP1B MED12	p.K57N (c.171G>T) p.L795del (c.2383_2385del) p.T783Rfs*5 (c.2348_2351del) p.R63H (c.188G>A) p.R2389T (c.7166G>C) p.Y1998C (c.5993A>G)	6.4 1.7 46.5 52.9 49.1 100.0	
10	38	M	right neck (m)	II, IV	II	pain, swelling	no	no	RIT1	p.E98 T100delinsVPL (c.293_299delinsAGTTTAC)	6.0	interstitial progression + hypertrophy after treatment bilateral involvement
11	34	M	both legs (sc, b)	CV	III	pain, atypical varicosis	no	no	PTPN11 SDHA PDGFRB NCOR1	p.Ser502Pro (c.1504T>C) p.Asn108Ser (c.323A>G) p.Trp566Arg (c.1696T>C) p.Ser1943Leu (c.5828C>T)	5.1 1.5 1.5 49.8	
12	51	M	Right leg and foot (sc)	II (IV)	III	pain, swelling, ulceration, recurrent infections	yes	yes	KRAS TP53 EPCAM (MAP3K14-AS1) INSR EML4	p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A) p.Arg175His (c.524G>A) p.Thr113Asn (c.338C>A) NA (n.2039A>C) p.Ile639Phe (c.1915A>T) p.Asp976Gly (c.2927A>G)	1.8 1.8 2.0 42.8 47.4 43.3	elongated feeder arteries
13	29	F	right leg (sk, sc, m)	IIIb, II, IV	I V	pain, recurrent ulceration, recurrent infection	yes	yes	KRAS MRE11A CCND3 BCL2L11 FBN1 (germline)	p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A) p.Asp60Ala (c.179A>C) p.Ser259Ala (c.774_775delinsTG) p.Arg185Gly (c.553C>G) p.Cys887Tyr (c.2660G>A)	12.4 46.0 46.8 50.7	Marfan syndrome; aneurysms of feeder arteries; interstitial progression after treatment
14	58	F	right leg and foot (sc)	CV	III	recurrent ulceration, atypical varicosis	yes	yes	KRAS	p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A)	3.2	
15	50	M	right hand (sc, m)	IIIb, II, IV	III	pain	yes	yes	KRAS CEBPA SF3B1 PBRM1	p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A) p.Leu178Arg (c.533T>G) p.Arg115Trp (c.343C>T) p.Ala1292Ser (c.3874_3876delinsTCT)	8.8 43.4 48.3 41.7	aneurysms of feeder arteries;
16	46	F	nose (sk, sc)	II	III	pain, ulceration	no	no	KRAS HNF1A LRP1B NCOA3 VHL TNFAIP3	p.Gly12Asp (c.35G>A) p.Pro308Leu (c.923C>T) p.Gly2111Arg (c.6331G>C) p.Asn263Asp (c.787A>G) p.Arg205Cys (c.613C>T) p.Arg87Gln (c.260G>A)	11.5 45.8 49.9 46.9 48.6 49.3	
17	39	F	right leg (m, sc)	II (CV)	II	pain	yes	yes	KRAS FAT1 BRCA2 EPHA5	p.Gly12Val (c.35G>T) p.Glu904Ter (c.2710G>T) p.Glu1120Gln (c.3358G>C) p.Tyr650Ter (c.1950C>A)	4.7 1.6 52.1 47.5	additional spinal AVM

18	18	M	Left leg (sc, m)	IIIb, II	III	pain, ulceration, infection, atypical varicosis	yes	yes	KRAS <i>MSH6</i> <i>PREX2</i> <i>MYC</i> <i>ANKRD26</i> <i>ANKRD26</i> <i>TET1</i> <i>PIK3C2G</i> <i>SH2B3</i> <i>PALB2</i> <i>BBC3</i>	p.G12D (c.35G>A) p.K22E (c.64A>G) p.I173M (c.519A>G) p.K158R (c.473A>G) NA (c.1269+8_1269+12del) NA (c.1269+7T>A) p.N661H (c.1981A>C) p.A136P (c.406G>C) p.R425C (c.1273C>T) p.T787I (c.2360C>T) p.P247L (c.740C>T)	9.0 48.0 48.6 51.3 44.0 42.9 49.0 45.9 48.8 50.2 47.2	
19	41	F	right leg (sk, sc, m)	CV	II	pain, overgrowth	yes	yes	RASA1 <i>MED12</i>	p.P886Afs*12 (c.2654dupG) p.Q2120H (c.G6360C)	6.2 4.4	PKWS: CM, AVM, overgrowth
20	22	F	left leg right foot right arm (sc)	IIIb	II	pain, swelling	no	no	PTEN <i>(germline)</i> <i>PIK3CG</i> <i>KAT6A</i> <i>TRAF2</i>	c.635-2A>C p.Arg19Lys(c.56G>A) p.Gly1441Asp (c.4322G>A) p.Pro9Ala (c.25C>G)	50.4 49.1 48.4 38.3	PTEN- Hamartoma- Tumor- Syndrom (PHTS)
21	39	F	left leg and foot (sk, sc, m)	CV	III	pain, recurrent ulcerations	yes	yes	PIK3CA <i>SDHC</i>	p.Arg108_Ile112del (c.323_337del) p.Tyr99Asn (c.295T>A)	10.5 1.4	PKWS: CM, AVM, overgrowth
22	33	F	Right leg (m)	CV	I	pain	no	no	PIK3CA <i>MGA</i> <i>PIK3C2G</i> <i>TSHR</i> <i>AXL</i>	p.E545K (c.1633G>A) p.D2061G (c.6182A>G) p.R1467Q (c.4400G>A) p.L57P (c.170T>C) p.K439R (c.1316A>G)	1.3 1.0 46.9 50.7 48.2	
23	57	F	left hand (sc)	CV	I	pain	no	no	CREBBP <i>DNMT3B</i> <i>SOX10</i> <i>QKI</i> <i>TSC1</i> <i>MED12</i> <i>STAG2</i> <i>ALOX12B</i> <i>SETBP1</i> <i>LRP1B</i> <i>PRKN</i>	p.Arg1774His (c.5321G>A) p.Arg92Trp (c.274C>T) p.Arg215Gln (c.644G>A) p.Asp24del (c.70_72del) p.Arg517Gln (c.1550G>A) p.Arg1467Gln (c.4400G>A) p.Cys308Tyr (c.923G>A) p.Arg548Trp (c.1642C>T) p.Arg987Gln (c.2960G>A) p.Pro4118Leu (c.12353C>T) p.Arg104Trp (c.310C>T)	3.0 3.8 4.8 4.9 3.2 3.7 5.0 44.2 46.7 50.0 44.4	
24	58	M	right foot (it, b, sc)	II	III	ischemic bone erosion	yes	no	MDC1 <i>DDR2</i>	p.P1177S (c.3528_3529delinsAT) p.G575R (c.G1723C)	1.8 45.4	elongated feeder arteries
25	49	F	upper and lower lip (m)	II	II	bleeding	no	no	SMC3 <i>FBXW7</i> <i>FANCA</i>	p.R1154G (c.3460A>G) p.V504F (c.1510G>T) p.L1320del (c.3959_3961del)	4.2 5.2 43.2	
26	30	M	left leg (sk, sc, m)	IIIb, II, IV	III	pain, swelling, recurrent ulcerations	yes	yes	PTPRD <i>RET</i> <i>ARID5B</i> <i>DDX41</i> <i>VEGFA</i>	p.I1192V (c.3574A>G) p.S832R (c.2496C>G) p.A1009V (c.3026C>T) p.H91N (c.271C>A) p.T8I (c.23C>T)	1.1 48.6 49.5 49.1 45.2	PKWS: CM, AVM, overgrowth
27	34	F	left thoracic wall (m)	IIIb, II	II	pain, swelling	yes	no	H3C12 <i>PRKDC</i> <i>NOTCH1</i> <i>TCF3</i> <i>ASXL1</i> <i>SPEN</i> <i>PRKDC</i>	p.M1? (c.3G>A) p.A3898V (c.11693C>T) p.K814E (c.2440A>G) p.T79I (c.236C>T) p.P1123L (c.3368C>T) p.R871C (c.2611C>T) p.E1050del (c.3148_3150del)	2.7 1.7 1.5 45.6 47.9 48.2 42.7	
28	44	M	Neck (it)	II	II	pain	yes	no	ADGRA2 <i>PRKDC</i> <i>NOTCH1</i> <i>BMPR1A</i> <i>ERBB3</i> <i>NUP93</i> <i>MED12</i>	p.P915T (c.2743C>A) p.A3898V (c.11693C>T) p.K814E (c.2440A>G) p.S182G (c.544A>G) p.A1337T (c.4009G>A) p.G591V (c.1772G>T) p.R819Q (c.2456G>A)	2.0 49.5 49.0 51.8 48.3 47.6 100.0	
29	29	F	lung (vo)	II	I	asymptomatic	no	no	BRAF <i>IKZF1</i>	p.Arg146Trp (c.436C>T) p.Asp22Asn (c.64>A)	52.9 50.4	

30	42	M	right foot (sc)	IIIb	II	pain	no	no	<u>MAP3K13</u>	<u>p.Pro17GlnfsTer41</u>	45.4	elongated feeder arteries								
									<u>ANKRD11</u>	<u>(c.49_50insAA)</u>	49.0									
									<u>TCF3</u>	<u>p.Asp540Tyr (c.1618G>T)</u>	48.4									
									<u>ROS1</u>	<u>p.Pro633Leu (c.1898C>T)</u>	44.8									
									<u>ARID1B</u>	<u>p.Phe502Ser (c.1505T>C)</u>	50.0									
31	24	M	left arm (it,b)	II, IIIb	II	pain	yes	no	<u>FYN</u>	<u>p.Thr78Arg (c.233C>G)</u>	45.6									
									<u>FAT1</u>	<u>p.Asp4377Asn (c.13129G>A)</u>	45.4									
									32	8	F	right Hand (sc)	CV	II	pain, swelling	no	no	<u>PIK3CG</u>	<u>p.Val1065GlyfsTer9</u>	46.3
																		<u>ARID2</u>	<u>(c.3194_3195del)</u>	48.6
																		<u>ERBB3</u>	<u>p.Gly1110Asp</u>	50.5
<u>DNMT1</u>	<u>(c.3329_3330delinsAT)</u>	48.8																		
33	19	M	left ear (sc)	II	III	pain, swelling, papillomatous skin changes	no	no	<u>ABRAXAS1</u>	<u>p.Arg148Ter (c.442C>T)</u>	46.3									
									<u>DIS3</u>	<u>p.Arg12Gly (c.34C>G)</u>	49.5									
									<u>LATS1</u>	<u>p.Ser139Cys (c.415A>T)</u>	48.0									
									34	21	F	left foot (m)	IIIb	II	pain	no	no	<u>ZBTB7A</u>	<u>p.Val311Met (c.931G>A)</u>	50.3
																		35	56	M

Summary of tables I and II with additionally detected variants with VAF (variant allele frequency) > 20%. Affected tissue compartments are abbreviated as follows (sk = skin, sc = subcutaneous tissue, it = interstitial space, m = muscle, vo = visceral organs, b = bone). Angiographic classification is displayed according to Yakes types I to IV with the addition of CV (capillary-venule AVM); mutations, previously reported in AVMs, are in **bold and underlined**; potentially significant new variants are underlined; additional VUS (variants of unknown significance) are displayed in normal writing.

Figure 1: Overview of the four patients with new variants in the context of AVM.

Patient images are shown, as well as representative digital subtraction angiography (DSA) images: (a) arterial phase, (b) nidus/nidi, (c) venous phase. From left to right: *RIT1* mutation in a patient with an intramuscular AVM type II and IV in the right splenius capitis and -cervicis. *PTPN11* mutation in a patient with subcutaneous CV-AVM in both calves (DSA of the right calf is shown). *PIK3CA* mutation in a female patient with an extensive capillary malformation, left leg circumferential and longitudinal overgrowth and microfistular CV-AVM). Combined *PTEN* and *GNAQ* mutation in a male patient with an extensive dark capillary malformation, left leg circumferential and longitudinal overgrowth and microfistular CV-AVM).

Figure 2: Genotypic comparison of AVM type IIIb of the foot.

Three patients with isolated AVM type IIIb of the foot are shown with patient images and corresponding representative digital subtraction angiography images: (a) arterial phase, (b) venous phase.

Figure 3: Phenotypic comparison of *KRAS* and *MAP2K1* AVMs.

Patient images are shown, as well as corresponding representative digital subtraction angiography images: (a) arterial phase, (b) venous phase.

Figure 4: Hypertrophy versus blood filled vessel volume.

A: shows the hands of a patient 3 with circumferential swelling due to blood filled vessel volume; (a) MRI - T1 fat saturated steady state angiography; (b) MRI - T1 arterial twist angiography.

B: shows in contrast soft tissue and longitudinal overgrowth of the right hand in patient 12 with AVM type IIIb, II and IV; (a) MRI - T1 fat saturated steady state angiography; (b) MRI - T1 arterial twist angiography.